

Developing and Implementing a Standardized Triage Model in OB Triage

Eun K. Yang, DNP, RN

Elizabeth J. Winokur, Ph.D., RN, CEN

Ayman Tailakh, Ph.D., RN

Background

Problems

- Wide range of patient acuity and volume
- Sudden change in nursing workload
- Overcrowded
- First come, first serve

Recommendation

- Acuity-based triage intake

Purpose

To optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in OB triage

Framework

PARIHS Model

Method

Setting

- Labor & Delivery Unit in Los Angeles, CA
- Approximately 7500 triage visits annually

Sample

- 43 RNs
- 150 available medical records

Implementation

- Maternal Fetal Triage Intake Algorithm
- Workflow Change

Data Collection

RN Assessment

- Accuracy rate, over- or under-triaged, chief complaints from under-triaged patients

Length of Stay

- Time to RN assessment, Time to departure

Patient Outcomes

- Adverse outcomes, improper discharge, maternal and newborn outcomes

Data Analysis: Descriptive Statistics

Results

RN Assessment

- 85% accuracy rate of the RN's assessment ($n = 128$)
- Most misriage occurred in mid-levels of 2 to 4 ($n = 13$)
- Most under-triage occurred in level 2 ($n = 10$)
- Chief complaints under-triaged
 - Preterm labor ($n = 7$), decreased fetal movement, ($n = 3$), falls ($n = 3$)

	n	%
Over- triaged ($n = 9, 40.9\%$)		
Day Shift	6	66.7%
Night Shift	3	33.3%
Under- triaged ($n = 13, 59.1\%$)		
Day Shift	11	84.6%
Night Shift	2	15.4%

Distribution of Inaccurate Assessment

MFTI Level Assigned	MFTI Level Corrected	n	%
3	2	6	46.2%
4	2	4	30.8%
	3	2	15.4%
5	4	1	7.7%

Breakdown of Under-triaged

Length of Stay

- 77% decrease in RN's assessment: from 22 minutes to 5 minutes
- No changes in the total length of stay

Patient Outcomes

- No adverse patients' outcomes due to inaccurate or delayed triage services

Discussion

RN Assessment

- 85% acceptable accuracy rate (Ruhl et al., 2015)
- Immediate attention needed to mistriaged (over- or under-triaged)
- 3 chief complaints under-triaged: Preterm labor, fetal movement, and falls (level corrected: URGENT/PRIORITY 2)

Length of Stay

- 77% reduction in RN assessment: Significant improvement allowing earlier identification of issues
- No changes in total length of stay: May reflect other contributing factors to triage delays

Patient Outcomes

- No adverse patients' outcomes due to inaccurate or delayed triage services: May reflect a successful MFTI implementation

Limitations

- Single site implementation
- Sampling/Membership bias

Future Studies

- Identify factors contributing to triage delays
- Assess total length of stay by subsets

Summary

- Safety was enhanced
- Incremental assessment and evaluations will require for ongoing improvement

References available upon request
yangek@csu.fullerton.edu